

An Effective Method of Quality Management in the Field of Road Construction Works

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Abstract:

Currently, effective management of quality and reliability in the field of road construction work is one of the important and strategic sectors of the country's economy. Solving the problem of road construction quality requires an integrated approach to project management, as well as the maximum requirement of construction principles and rules from customers and contractors. We consider one of the non-standard approaches to solving the current problem of effective quality management in the field of road construction, associated with expert assessment, which will lead to the creation of convenience and comfort in the life of the city population. The new approach is relevant and important due to the need to improve the road construction management system, as well as to create a market economic mechanism for assessing the quality and efficiency of road construction.

Keywords: Management efficiency, digitalization, information technology, information system, quality of road construction works, road construction project management, expert method, expert scoring, questionnaires.

Introduction

In all countries of the world, the effectiveness of quality management of road construction is a vital and socially significant sector of the economy, ensuring that the needs of the public economy in freight and passenger transportation are met, as well as creating safe, convenient and comfortable movement of people in them. The efficiency and quality of road construction work is ensured and carried out with the active participation of government authorities and private business structures. It is a complex industrial, technical and socio-economic complex, which includes the following

components: road construction and repair and maintenance production; external improvement and routine road cleaning; monitoring system and major road repairs; communication and control systems; environmental and sanitary-epidemiological control, as well as social and technical infrastructure for routine road repairs. Currently, road construction is a special branch of the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which employs thousands of citizens throughout the country. They ensure uninterrupted operation of the entire engineering infrastructure of facilities, which includes not only roads, but also administrative complexes, production facilities, and social buildings. The key task of road construction is to create comfortable conditions for favorable human life, providing space and safe movement of the population around the city. In the republic, to provide the population with high-quality and safe roads, as well as to create a market economic mechanism for assessing the effectiveness of road construction, it is carried out with the direct participation of government authorities and private business structures. The state must create conditions for the formation of an effective workable legal and legislative framework for the field of road construction. One of the main problems facing the authorities is the improvement of contractual relations between Customers and Contractors. The low quality and weak legal framework regulating public legal relations is one of the main reasons for the ineffectiveness of the operation of city roads. In this regard, the activity of citizens to directly participate in the management of road construction is increasing in order to reduce costs and improve quality.

Organizers and developers of technical road construction projects consider the road construction management system to be the main effective methods of strategic planning. The quality of construction is the development of efficient and transparent investments in real sectors of the economy one of the cornerstones. According to the international project standards “PMBok” (Project Management Body of Knowledge, PMBoK) and a number of other national and international standards, the goal of any project is to satisfy the requirements of the Project Customer. This goal is achieved by ensuring quality management and the final result of this project. Quality is a synthetic indicator that reflects the combined manifestation of various factors in a given process. It is known that the main indicators that reflect the quality of any project are: purpose, reliability, manufacturability, standardization, unification, safety, etc. The quality of road construction work is assessed on the basis of a quantitative measurement of its defining properties, where the final product is a road with a complex of various auxiliary structures and devices. Within the framework of the general concept, the quality of a road should be understood as a set of properties that determine its suitability to meet the needs of the public economy in freight and passenger transportation, loads and traffic intensity at minimal cost, as well as providing comfortable space and safe movement of the population around the city. It should be emphasized that recently innovative methods and high-quality materials have been successfully used in the construction of highways in the cities of Uzbekistan. Road construction project processes are accompanied by regularly scheduled inspections by the relevant organizations to determine compliance of the work with all regulatory requirements. At the same time, these organizations report monthly to the Customer on the progress of the design work, and also draw up an acceptance certificate for the operation of the construction road. Only strict adherence to the rules of work and the specified technological process can be ensured by the production discipline of all project participants. [1,2,3].

The global construction industry is currently undergoing a process of fundamental transformation. There is a transition from traditional design methods with the preparation and subsequent application of design documentation to the use of information modeling technologies for buildings and structures. This makes it possible to generate design, estimate and as-built documentation as a single information resource of an object throughout its life cycle, including the stages of operation and decommissioning. Therefore, solving the problem of road construction quality requires an integrated and systematic approach to project management throughout the entire life cycle with the widespread use of modern information technology technologies (ICT). However, the prospects for

the development of information technology in construction and, in particular, the road sector, at the level of world standards are still disappointing. And even those various automated systems that are used today in the construction complex of Uzbekistan do not meet modern requirements: they, for example, do not provide for the implementation of the function of social orientation of the population and protection of consumer rights. But this is one of the priority areas of urban planning reform. Most implemented systems do not provide dynamic adjustment to the constantly changing legislation and regulatory framework and do not provide, say, transparency of the process of the entire life cycle of road construction. Experts assess the level of development of information technologies in the road construction industry as low; in many regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, such technologies are not available at all, information about the condition of roads is not structured. All these problems existed before, but under market conditions they have sharply worsened. Сложившаяся негативная ситуация тормозит внедрение самых передовых мировых информационных систем в строительстве дорог. Therefore, this sector of the economy, according to many experts, is in a stagnant state, historically due to a number of circumstances:

- excessive concentration of management at the level of local executive authorities and state monopoly on property;
- weak technical base, lack of industry capacity and control over the use of resources;
- lack of necessary financial resources for strategic development and unreasonably high costs for maintaining road construction facilities;
- ineffective mechanism for setting tariffs and payment for work performed;
- discrepancy between prices and tariffs for services and the actual costs of their production;
- weak development of market relations and lack of effective economic incentives;
- lack of modern scientific and technical management and protection of consumer interests;
- lack of a competitive environment when introducing market mechanisms based on information technology;

Only the elimination of the above negative reasons will improve the efficiency of road construction management, which ensures favorable human life, as well as the stable functioning of the social and industrial infrastructure of the territory [4,5,6,7].

Among the problems that need to be solved during the implementation of economic reform, a special place is occupied by the reliability and accessibility of information, as well as the transition of the reform process to a qualitatively new market state. This problem can be successfully solved only on the basis of advanced information technologies. The introduction of modern information technologies will make it possible to create a qualitatively new system for managing city and regional construction, as well as a system of regulated interaction with executive bodies of state power. Modern information technologies should provide monitoring of the condition of the building stock, utility networks and road communications, control of payments for work performed, as well as information support for the management decision-making process. Consequently, the systematic use of modern ICT in the management of road construction will lead to qualitative changes in the life of the population, and will also significantly improve the quality, speed and transparency of monitoring the construction of road works in Uzbekistan. Today, the republic is undergoing a phased automation of all areas of construction activities, as well as their accounting for all types of services. The systematic implementation of web portals - the construction portal of Uzbekistan (stroyka.uz), the open data portal (my.gov.uz) and regulations (regulation.gov.uz), etc. is an example of the state providing mechanisms of openness, transparency and feedback from the population. The created single online information portal will make it possible, at the first stage, to make available information on the state of road construction in real time. Thus, the modern global

digital economy is radically changing our ideas about familiar things. New terms and methods appear that can best explain the processes taking place. More recently, the term “road” was defined as “an engineering structure intended for the movement of cars.” The peculiarity of the new technological revolution lies in the engineering and socio-economic integration of related systems. Today, a highway is an object of centralized transport infrastructure designed for the movement of various vehicles. For some time, the object of research in the road industry was: driver - car - road, today it is a system: people - loads - traffic flows - transport infrastructure - digital economy. The key technologies ensuring digitalization of the road industry are information modeling (BIM - Building Information Modeling) and intelligent transport systems (ITS - Intelligent transportation system). BIM information modeling technology affects the activities of mainly road engineers; ITS serve as a digital tool, primarily for automotive and transport engineers. Consequently, the junction of these two areas of activity can be provided, in the language of IT specialists, by the integration bus “Digital Highway. Therefore, at present, digitalization in road construction is still the subject of numerous discussions and debates among specialists. Solving the problem of construction quality requires an integrated approach to project management, with priority given to the requirements of project customers [8,10,11,12].

Currently, an important criterion for the efficiency of road construction is a functional platform, that is, complete automation of the entire cycle of work processes. Transparency in the expenditure of planned funds is achieved using the module for monitoring work on obligations, which implies confirmation of the completion of work through the system using photos, video recording and other control tools, according to which expense items, it becomes possible to control the expenditure of funds at each stage of work. In addition, you can make various statistical calculations on the actual work performed for the project manager. Contractors must also have access to the platform. They must also be able to control the work process. One of the most important control tools is a mobile application, with which the contractor can receive tasks, as well as send photos and videos to the system confirming the completion of work. In fact, contractors can use such solutions for their own needs, for example, if internal control of employees of a construction site is necessary. As for technology, the system should be based on a register containing all information on objects, contracts, contractors and the current state of road network objects. And this is one of their main and key advantages, which increases the transparency and quality of road construction work. At the same time, compliance with regulatory and technological requirements for road construction does not guarantee their proper quality. In road construction, a rather complex system is used to assess the compliance of the work performed with the project and the quality of the road surface. This leads to a decrease in the durability of city roads and an increase in their cost. The efficiency of using these loan funds is related, among other things, to the quality of road construction work. In our opinion, it is necessary to improve the project management system for the construction of internal roads by attracting a wide range of independent and competent expert specialists.

Technical control is a set of guidelines for determining the quality indicators of roads, materials used, technological processes and finished products and comparing them with the requirements of technical specifications and standards. Systematic planned technical control allows you to more effectively manage the quality of construction of city roads. However, for some reason, observing all the regulatory rules and technology of the construction process, during operation, the city roads of Uzbekistan are radically different in quality and durability from foreign analogues and standards. As a result, it turns out that either our technologies and road construction standards are much outdated, or are simply not suitable for our climatic latitudes, or most importantly, corrupt structures are successfully involved in the preparation of project documentation or tenders. At the same time, in the construction of roads, corruption, figuratively speaking, takes part unnoticed and is very difficult to detect. Meanwhile, corruption in road construction can only be detected after a very thorough and objective independent expert analysis. Here, we agree that the main problem is the excessive appetites of corrupt officials who make money from road construction by lobbying the

interests of other competitive construction companies. As a result, the cost of completed road construction work increases, and the quality is very different from the standard indications [3,20,21,22].

The most important aspect of a road is to consider its actual cost and how long it will last. Therefore, we offer an optimal and effective bottom-up approach to management and quality control of the entire life cycle of road construction works. The essence of the method is as follows: firstly, after the development of design documentation for road construction projects, it is necessary that it undergo state examination, in accordance with the construction regulations. After the bidding (tender), usually an electronic auction, the winning design organization (Contractor) begins to implement this road construction project. Further, competent construction specialists - independent experts - must participate in assessing and analyzing the quality of the road construction process. Selective expert survey is carried out at all stages of the life cycle of road construction works:

- ✓ in the process of developing design and estimate documentation;
- ✓ to assess the quality of raw materials, materials and manufactured products;
- ✓ during construction and installation work;
- ✓ at the stage of road operation.

From the above, we can assume that the proposed new “bottom-up” approach is an effective, efficient and effective method for managing the quality assessment of road construction. The main goal of the “bottom-up” method is to combine all the main processes of road construction into a single quality management plan called “plan - cost control” based on expert assessment methods. Each stage of completed road construction work must represent a combination of all the most important parts of the whole project. When choosing a strategy for managing and ensuring quality, construction roads of the city. The contractor is guided by the Approved design and estimate documentation and the construction project. The construction project ensures the efficiency and focus of all organizational, technical and technological solutions to achieve the final result, with the required quality, on time, and at a minimum cost.

Road management and quality control is a complex, scientific, technical, economic and social problem. The production of road construction products has significant specificity, since design and survey, production, supply, construction and installation, subcontracting, operational and other organizations that are separated territorially and administratively participate in the construction of roads. Therefore, the project must represent a single chain, starting from individual local organizational and technical measures to continuously operating activities within large construction organizations. Consequently, the quality of the road should be considered at various levels aimed at meeting certain production, economic and social requirements. It is important that when performing road construction work in cities and towns, the requirements for the comfort and safety of roads in adjacent areas must be met. Therefore, the proposed expert method is used when road quality indicators cannot be determined due to insufficient reliable information and the impossibility or inappropriateness of assessment under specific conditions, as well as avoiding the above negative consequences. [8,9,14,].

However, it is not clear why, despite observing all the regulatory rules and technology, at the operational stage our city roads differ so much in quality, durability and in terms of space and convenience for citizens. Based on the above critical assessments, we propose an integrated and effective bottom-up approach, namely management and quality control of road construction works based on expert assessment methods using the example of the city of Samarkand. The main goal of the method is that initially, after the development of design documentation for road construction projects, it is necessary that it pass all stages of state examination on schedule. After this, during the entire life cycle of construction, competent specialists - independent construction experts - should

be involved in assessing and analyzing the quality of road construction works. Statistical processing of the final results of road construction, obtained from expert scores, confirms that expert methods are the most effective and optimal tools for determining the quality indicators of road construction.

Currently, the expert method of assessing the quality and control of construction roads in project management is a scientifically based method for analyzing complex non-formalized problems. An expert is a repository of a large amount of objective and rationally processed information and therefore can be considered a quality source. The group opinion of experts (more than 35 experts) is close to the true solution to the problem. The main types of the expert assessment method include: questioning, interviewing, brainstorming, discussion, meeting, operational game and scenario. Each of these expert assessment methods has its own advantages and disadvantages, which determine the rational scope of application. To construct survey procedures and data processing algorithms, methods of measurement theory and mathematical statistics are usually used. The generalized judgment of experts obtained as a result of statistical processing is accepted as a solution to problems. When using the expert method in practice to assess the quality of roads, a working and expert group is formed. The working group organizes the procedure for interviewing experts, collects questionnaires, processes and analyzes expert assessments. The expert group is formed from highly qualified and competent specialists in the field of construction work. It is very important that the expert group is formed not for one examination, but as a permanently functioning body with a stable composition of experts. To obtain reliable results, a scientifically based system of questioning experts is required. Processing of data received from experts serves as the source material for confirming the reliability, strength and quality of operation of construction roads. The article also shows that in order to obtain maximum efficiency in the quality of construction roads, it is necessary to establish a quantitative or point scale for all used indicators of the quality of work. Then the sum of the scores of each factor and the total score are determined. Next, the weight coefficients of the scores of each factor are estimated and the results are checked by summation. Below is an example where a questionnaire was compiled to survey competent experts on the quality of road construction in the city of Samarkand for 2022. The questionnaire consists of 23 questions, and the experts' answers (more than 35) are recorded on a 10-point scale for all expert members participating in the survey (1-min point, 10-max point). [3,8,9,14,].

The questionnaire includes the following topical issues of road construction in the city:

1. How do you assess the reliability and technical safety of the city's automobile and pedestrian roads?
2. How do you assess the efficiency and quality of the road construction network management system in Uzbekistan?
3. How do you rate the convenience and comfort of the city's pedestrian road space?
4. Is it necessary to create parks and boulevards taking into account the parking zones of roads that have national specifics?
5. Is it necessary to develop the level of improvement and procedure for landscaping the territory of roads, taking into account the historical integrated design of the regional climatic and natural conditions of the city?
6. Is it necessary to maintain the environmental friendliness and quality of the road, taking into account local climatic and natural conditions?
7. Is it necessary to introduce qualitatively new principles and rules for organizing road construction work based on advanced foreign analogues?
8. Necessary organization of parking zones for cars and passenger vehicles, established requirements for public transport stops, kiosks and other non-stationary objects?

9. Necessary improvement of approaches to the integrated development of sections of highways, pedestrian and bicycle paths, taking into account advanced foreign experience?
10. Have the ideas you developed to improve the road and pedestrian routes for people been adopted?
11. Are you satisfied with the quality of the implemented highway and pedestrian road projects in the republic?
12. How do you assess the need to assess the efficiency and quality of highway and pedestrian road facilities in accordance with national standards?
13. Is it necessary to develop national innovative road construction projects that develop digital infrastructure and technology?
14. How do you assess the level of competence of the leaders of the road construction service of the republic?
15. How do you assess the level of knowledge of the engineering and technical staff and specialist experts of the road construction service of the republic?
16. Is it necessary to develop market-based methodological instructions for assessing the effectiveness and monitoring of road construction projects in the republic, taking into account resource support?
17. Is it necessary to increase the transparency of road construction project documentation and the efficiency of capital investments?
18. Is it necessary to introduce information modeling technologies into engineering and management construction processes and motivate their participants?
19. Necessary development of national innovative enterprises developing digital infrastructure and technologies in road construction?
20. Do you need potential integration with different management solutions using modern CAD-BIM products?
21. Is there corruption in the structures of road construction management in Uzbekistan?
22. Have you personally encountered corrupt officials in the republic's road construction?
23. Have you personally given bribes to corrupt officials in the city's road construction?

Table 1. Expert scores of factors

Experts Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
1	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	5	7	8	6	7	8	6
2	7	8	7	6	5	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	7	8	6	5
3	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	5	8	7	6	7	5
4	7	6	7	8	6	7	6	7	8	7	8	6	6	7	8	6	8	7
5	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	6	5	7	8	6
6	7	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	8	6	7	8	6	7	5
7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	6
8	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	6	7	8	5	6	7	8	6	7
9	8	6	7	8	6	7	6	7	8	6	7	6	7	8	6	7	6	8
10	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	7	8	5	7	6	7	8	6	7	6	7
11	6	7	8	5	7	8	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7
12	8	7	8	7	8	6	7	6	7	8	7	8	7	6	7	6	7	6
13	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	8	6	7	8
14	8	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	7	6	8	7	6	7	8	7

15	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	8	7	6
16	8	7	6	7	8	7	6	5	7	8	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6
17	7	8	6	8	7	8	8	6	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8
18	8	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6
19	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	8	7	6	7	8	6	7
20	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8
21	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	7
22	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6
23	7	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	7	8	6	7	8	7	6
TOTAL	165	160	158	167	160	159	165	155	160	165	163	158	158	161	158	159	164	150

Continuation of Table 1.

19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	TOTAL
7	8	8	7	6	7	8	7	6	7	5	6	7	8	6	5	6	239
5	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	5	7	6	7	8	7	8	240
6	7	8	7	5	7	8	6	7	8	9	7	8	6	5	6	7	241
7	8	9	8	6	7	8	9	7	6	7	8	6	5	7	8	9	250
6	7	8	9	8	7	6	5	7	8	6	6	8	7	7	8	8	244
6	8	9	7	8	8	7	6	8	7	7	7	8	6	7	8	9	250
5	6	7	7	8	8	7	6	7	8	9	7	8	6	7	8	9	249
7	8	9	8	7	9	8	7	6	7	8	7	8	7	6	5	7	246
6	7	8	9	8	7	8	6	7	8	9	6	7	8	7	8	7	250
7	8	9	8	7	6	7	8	6	7	9	8	7	8	7	6	7	250
8	6	7	8	7	6	7	9	8	7	8	9	6	7	8	9	8	250
7	8	9	8	7	6	5	7	8	7	8	7	6	7	9	8	7	250
5	6	7	8	8	7	8	6	5	6	7	8	9	7	6	7	8	245
7	8	8	7	8	9	9	8	7	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	7	253
6	7	8	9	6	7	8	9	8	9	7	8	7	8	6	7	8	257
7	8	9	6	7	8	9	6	7	8	9	6	7	8	9	6	7	252
7	8	6	7	8	9	8	6	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	8	252
8	7	6	7	8	7	8	6	8	7	5	6	7	8	9	7	6	246
5	6	7	7	8	9	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	6	7	245
7	8	6	7	6	7	8	9	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	7	8	251
8	6	7	6	7	8	9	8	6	8	7	6	7	8	7	6	7	248
7	6	7	8	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	6	241
7	8	6	8	6	7	8	7	6	7	8	5	6	7	6	7	7	242
151	166	176	172	161	170	176	161	158	167	169	160	162	162	164	160	171	5691

The final quantification of the factor is determined using the simple ranking method, the data are shown in Table 1. Using the method of mathematical statistics, we obtain a generalized opinion of experts. The average rank of each factor and the average statistical value of the Sj factor are determined.

$$S_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{35} a_{ij}}{m_j}$$

where Sj is the average value of the factors, aij is the expert's assessment of the factor.

mj is the number of experts assessing the j-th factor, i is the number of the expert,

j - factor number. After processing the data from Table 1, the average rank of factors was:

S1=6,8; S2=6,9; S3=6,9; S4=7,1; S5=7,0; S6=7,1;

S7=7,1; S8=7,0; S9=7,1; S10=7,1; S11=7,0; S12=7,1;

S13=7,2; S14=7,0; S15=7,3; S16=7,2; S17=7,2; S18=7,0;

S19=7,0; S20=7,2; S21=7,1; S22=6,9; S23=6,9;

Mathematical and statistical processing of the final results of road construction, obtained from independent expert scores, is the basis that expert methods are the most effective and optimal tools for determining the quality indicators of road construction. Based on the results of the expert scoring, we can conclude that the general opinion of experts on the quality and reliability of Samarkand road construction is above the normative average, that is, at a satisfactory level. Consequently, the planned level of efficiency and quality of road construction must be balanced with the volume of consumer demand, determined by the actual solvency of potential consumers. As a result, it can be recommended that in Uzbekistan the standards and norms of urban planning in the field of improvement should be qualitatively updated at the legislative level based on advanced foreign analogues, taking into account the integrated design of the regional climatic and natural conditions of the city;

Based on this, it is proposed that the following requirements and recommendations should be included in city road construction projects, as well as in national regulatory guidelines and international standards:

- creating a comfortable and safe pedestrian space for people;
- organization of parking zones for cars and passenger vehicles;
- establishing regulatory requirements for public transport stops, kiosks and other non-stationary objects;
- improving approaches to integrated site development highways with pedestrian and bicycle paths, taking into account advanced foreign experience;
- procedure for landscaping the territory, taking into account the integrated design of the regional climatic and natural conditions of the city;
- introduction of qualitatively new principles and rules for organizing road construction work based on advanced foreign analogues;
- level of improvement and environmental safety of the area based on a synthesis of domestic and foreign experience;
- improving the vehicle network condition management system roads;
- increasing the efficiency of capital investments and transparency of road construction project documentation;
- introduction of information modeling technologies into management construction processes and motivation of their participants;
- supporting the development of national innovation projects that develop digital infrastructure, platforms and technologies;
- potential integration with various solutions, including those with national specifics, using modern CAD-BIM products.
- development of methodological recommendations for assessing effectiveness and monitoring of road works, taking into account resource support;

Summarizing the above, it can be assumed that the current construction industry in Uzbekistan has good potential for digitalization. A gradual transition to digital for economic reasons is overdue: despite many unfavorable factors, a significant number of the most progressive construction companies are introducing new technologies into their work, seeing their high potential and efficiency. Therefore, the work that has now begun at the state level to “legalize” information modeling technologies has a great chance of success. And, judging by the government’s plans

announced, the Uzbek road construction industry will finally enter the “digital era” in the coming years. [5,6,8].

To summarize, we can say that the expert method is an optimal and effective tool for managing the quality of a road construction project. Therefore, the expert method must be used as one of the new and non-standard approaches to solving the urgent problem of road construction, which will lead to qualitative changes in the life of the city population. Consequently, only an integrated “bottom-up” approach based on expert assessment methods, as well as the systematic use of modern ICT in the management of road construction works, will significantly improve the quality, speed and transparency of monitoring the construction of road works in Uzbekistan and is a determining criterion for the effectiveness and durability of their exploitation.

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